

Milestone MS5

Identification of Extreme Indicators for Task 3.2 “Marine extremes in Europe and the Arctic area”

MILESTONE

Milestone	MS5 Identification of Extreme Indicators for Task 3.2 Marine extremes in Europe and the Arctic area
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TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. Means of verification	3
2. What is this milestone about?	3
2.1 Indicators	3
2.2 Extreme Events	4
2.3 Extreme Indicators	4
3. Agreement on Extreme Indicators	5
3.1 Extreme Temperature	9
3.2 Extreme Sea Level	9
3.3 Extreme Sea Ice Loss	10
4. Contribution to the ObsSea4Clim objectives	11
5. References	13
Annex 1: Internal Survey Responses	15

1. Means of verification

As stated in the Description of the Action, the means to verify that this milestone has been achieved is the following: “A set of indicators for extremes has been agreed”.

2. What is this milestone about?

This milestone provides a list of indicators for extreme events in the ocean to be studied within WP3 and across the project.

2.1 Indicators

The Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS) currently defines ocean indicators as “measures based on scientifically verified approaches and data that allow for the identification of the state in ocean phenomena across a range of temporal and spatial scales that are accessible to inform decision makers and beyond” (von Schuckmann et al., in prep.). Proposed indicators from GOOS also included in the Global Climate Observing System (GCOS) Global Indicator Framework, include ocean warming, sea ice and sea level, and are derived from the Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs).

An example of widely-used indicators can be found on Copernicus Marine Service, the Ocean Monitoring Indicators (OMIs) “are free downloadable trends and datasets covering the past quarter of a century. These are key variables used to track the vital signs of the ocean and changes in line with climate change”¹.

The following set of criteria for indicators are currently being proposed within and beyond this project (von Schuckmann et al., in prep.): verified, significant, scalable, justified, measurable, and accessible.

¹ <https://marine.copernicus.eu/access-data/ocean-monitoring-indicators> Date of last access: 27/11/2024

2.2 Extreme Events

An extreme event occurs when a physical or biogeochemical variable crosses into a threshold which has some tangible impact on physical processes, ecosystem health or the economy. Besides this qualitative definition, there are key parameters to be defined. For example, the threshold may be an absolute value or a relative/statistical value, such as the 90th or 95th percentile, which is calculated over a given climatology period. Climatology refers to the typical (average) conditions over an extended period (typically 30 years or more), against which the term “extreme” can be defined. Climatology can be constructed with different frequencies (e.g. daily or monthly) and may be calculated over a fixed or moving period.

The question of how extremes fit into the existing and developing framework for ocean indicators is still open; for example, one could consider marine heatwaves as a sub-indicator of ocean warming. Besides these ongoing discussions on the indicator framework, a lack of conformity in defining extreme events has led to disagreement on the best approaches and potential confusion for stakeholders (e.g. regarding marine heatwaves; Amaya et al., 2023).

2.3 Extreme Indicators

We agree on the definition of extremes of **temperature**, **sea ice** and **sea level**, and the metrics/characteristics used to describe these extremes. Given the lack of an indicator framework for extremes, we use the qualitative definitions of extremes as preliminary extreme indicators. We agreed on set-up parameters for each extreme indicator: EOVS(s) used, temporal resolution, climatology frequency, climatology type, threshold, and metrics used to describe extreme indicators (Table 1). We allow for flexibility in the choice of these set-up parameters.

3. Agreement on Extreme Indicators

To reach the agreement, ObsSea4Clim project partners participated in three specific meetings. They also replied to a questionnaire gathering information on the climatology periods, thresholds, and data types used to create the extreme indicators. A sample of questions and answers is found in Annex 1.

Based on the responses and discussions, we recognise that the set-up of the extreme indicator's parameters depends on the application. As such, the consortium partners have agreed to the following recommendations.

A fixed climatology period is recommended for studies of the past few decades in which a climatology period is necessary. The exact period used depends on data availability and the target application. Although governing bodies provide recommendations (e.g., the WMO²) for climatology periods, they do not align with all products used in this project (e.g., Copernicus reanalysis; Annex 1). This can be applied to detrended data as well as original data, to separate the signal of long-term temperature changes from interannual variability (e.g., Amaya et al., 2023). When assessing climate projections and extreme events relative to a warming climate, moving climatologies are used to represent the changing climate since the use of a fixed climatology would not capture ongoing changes in the climate system (e.g., Rosello et al., 2023). The choice of thresholds also depends significantly on the application or impact of the study, and even within the project partners wish to employ a range of options (Annex 1).

² <https://wmo.int/media/news/wmo-publishes-global-update-of-climate-datasets>, last access 03/12/2024

The agreed set of extreme indicators and the recommended set-up parameters are shown in Table 1 and will be discussed in the following sub-sections. For each event, the Table shows the EOVS(s) used, temporal resolution, climatology frequency, climatology type, threshold, and metrics used to describe extreme indicators. For each event, we outline a series of common parameters, as well as recommendations and justifications.

Extreme Indicator	EOVs	Temporal Resolution	Climatology Frequency	Climatology Type	Threshold	Metrics
Extreme Temperature (Marine Heatwaves)	SST, subsurface temperature, OHC	Daily	Daily	Fixed/Moving	90/95/99 th percentile	Occurrence, intensity (anomaly w.r.t threshold), duration, cumulative intensity, area
Extreme Sea Level	SSH	minute/hourly	Tidal	Fixed/Moving	Generalised extreme value theory (block maxima), and generalised Pareto distribution (above 97.5% threshold level)	Occurrence, Return level/period
		Daily	Annual	Fixed/Moving	99 th percentile	
Extreme Sea Ice Loss	Sea Ice (SIC, SIE)	Daily	Monthly	Fixed	90/95/99 th percentile	SIE defined as the area with SIC>15%, max and minimum extent (i.e. March + September), open water days

	Sea Ice (SIT)	weekly	weekly	Fixed	90/95/99 th percentile	Annual maximum ice thickness
	Sea and Sea-Ice surface temperature*	Daily	Daily/Monthly	Fixed	90/95/99 th percentile	Intensity (anomaly w.r.t threshold)

Table 1: Extreme Indicators. (*) indicates *proposed* EOVs.

3.1 Extreme Temperature

This extreme indicator is commonly referred to as a marine heatwave (MHW). The indicator is constructed using the following EOVs at daily resolution: sea surface temperature (SST), subsurface temperature, or ocean heat content (OHC). The qualitative definition of an MHW, as suggested by Hobday et al., 2016, is as follows: “a prolonged discrete anomalously warm water event that can be described by its duration, intensity... and spatial extent”. Specifically, we chose the 90th percentile as the threshold and a 5-day minimum duration. We choose this method as it is best suited for intercomparison between regions and datasets with potential biases, and has already been widely adopted by the oceanographic community. Although higher thresholds have been used to avoid saturation of MHW days in climate projections (e.g., 99th percentile in Darmaraki et al., 2019), here we tackle this issue by using moving climatologies. The climatology is calculated for each calendar day, and its type can be fixed or moved depending on the application. However, we nonetheless explore using different thresholds (e.g. 95%) to study rarer events (Smith et al., 2024).

3.2 Extreme Sea Level

The definition of the extreme indicator “Extreme Sea Level” depends on the application and data source (Pinaridi et al., 2024). In ObsSea4Clim we consider two forms of sea level data: sea level at tide gauges and sea surface height (SSH) derived from satellite data. Other extreme sea levels, such as those from extreme waves at sea, are not considered here. Extreme sea levels at tides gauges are a combination of mean sea level, tides, and storm surges. Data is gathered at hourly to minute intervals. Both for tide gauges and for the satellite SSH extremes can be defined in two ways:

(1) block maxima, in which annual maxima (e.g. 99th annual percentile) and its anomaly with respect to the mean of annual percentiles are considered, well defined in Copernicus Marine Services for the estimation of extreme events³ or

(2) the peak over a specific threshold, in which the height of sea level above the climatological 90th percentile is considered.

The methodology for defining extremes in terms of their statistics differs depending on the type of extreme considered with General Extreme Value distributions fitted to the former, and Pareto distributions fitted to the latter (Mentaschi et al., 2016). From these Extreme Sea Level Indicators of Return Level and Return Period are defined.

3.3 Extreme Sea Ice Loss

Definitions of extremes for sea ice loss are sparse in the literature. Here, the aim is to identify the utility of various candidate extreme indicators. The most commonly used sea ice indicator is sea ice extent (SIE), which is derived from the ECV/EOV sea ice concentration (SIC). Previously, extreme cases of SIE have been identified using the 90th percentile as a threshold (and a fixed climatology) or by ranking the monthly mean SIE; these will serve as preliminary thresholds before others will be used to study rarer extremes (e.g. 95th). Other sea ice indicators can also be derived from SIC e.g. the number of open water days, and the freeze-up and break-up dates of the sea ice, but these indicators are less mature. Another important indicator is the sea ice thickness (SIT), and here we suggest looking at the annual maximum ice thickness. The combination of SIE and thickness brings information on the total sea ice volume, which, however, is challenging to observe directly and accurately. Sea and sea-ice surface temperatures are highly correlated with sea ice loss (both extent and thickness) and have a significant potential to provide new information in this regard. Different

³https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/OMI_EXTREME_SL_MEDSEA_slev_mean_and_anomaly_obs/description

methodologies for defining extremes will be tested and evaluated to identify the best indicator framework for extreme sea ice loss.

4. Contribution to the ObsSea4Clim objectives

This milestone contributes to the achievement of the following specific objectives of the project.

<p>#SO1</p>	<p>To develop ocean indicators, provide improved EOV/ECVs and evolve European ocean observing.</p>
<p>This milestone is instrumental to achieving this SO, as it is linked to the D3.2 that will come in later. This milestone defines the list of extreme indicators, the EOVs used to construct them, and the methods used to calculate them. Understanding the observational requirements to build these indicators will contribute to the work of WP4. The development and analysis of the listed indicators will be presented in D3.2.</p>	
<p>SO2</p>	<p>To advance the use of EOV and ECVs for improved ESM and reduced uncertainty in projections.</p>

<p>This milestone defines the list of indicators to be studied in Task 5.3, whose main objective is the skill assessment of extreme indicators in ESMs. This list is crucial to MS18 and D5.3.</p>	
SO3	<p>To create an interoperable data ecosystem serving multidisciplinary needs.</p>
<p>This milestone is instrumental to the achievement of this SO, as it is linked to the D3.3 that will come in later. This milestone advances the ocean indicator framework by extending to extreme events and will contribute to D3.3 on climatic impacts.</p>	
SO4	<p>To develop best practices and standards for interoperable in-situ and satellite observing.</p>
<p>This Milestone contributes to this SO by defining the ObsSea4Clim approach to developing ocean indicators as part of the unifying and interoperable framework for ocean observing.</p>	
SO5	<p>To place Europe in the forefront of the global coordination of the broader ocean-climate nexus.</p>

This milestone is instrumental to achieving this SO, as it is linked to the D3.1-D3.3 that will come in later.

5. References

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von Schuckmann et al. (GOOS task team on ocean indicators), 2024: Global Ocean Indicators: Marking Pathways at the Science-Policy Nexus, in preparation.

Annex 1: Internal Survey Responses

State the type of data.
20 responses

The WMO recommends 1991-2020 as a fixed climatology period - is this possible for your data?
19 responses

Which of the following climatologies do you intend to use?
20 responses

Please state the threshold you use to define extremes.
19 responses

Fig. A1: Responses to key questions from the survey on Extreme Event definitions sent to partners in WPs 3,4 & 5. 20 responses were received in total.